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Investigation of Photocatalytic Activity of Anchored Dysprosium and Praseodymium Complexes on CoFe₂O₄ in Synthesis of Pyrano[2,3-d]pyrimidine Derivatives

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Abstract

Two hitherto unknown magnetic nanoparticles were prepared through the immobilization of Dysprosium (Dy) and Praseodymium (Pr) Complexes on the surface of CoFe₂O₄, using commercially available or easily accessible materials under green conditions. They were fully characterized, using, FT-IR, SEM, EDX, ICP-OES, XRD and TGA techniques. Photocatalytic activity of these nanocomposites were successfully examined in the high yielding synthesis of pyrano[2,3-d]pyrimidines, via MCR, involving, barbituric acid, malononitrile and differently substituted benzaldehydes in the UV region (250 nm) at room temperature. The above-mentioned photocatalysts showed excellent recoverability and reusability under the optimal reaction conditions.

Keywords: CoFe₂O₄@Glutamine-Pr, Green synthesis, Nano catalyst, Photocatalyst, Pyrano[2,3-d]pyrimidine